

STUDIES ON GENETIC VARIABILITY, HERITABILITY AND GENETIC ADVANCE IN HOT CHILLI (*Capsicum annuum* L.)Rudra Patidar¹, Pushpendra Kumar^{1*}, Vinod Jatav¹, C.K. Sharma¹, Deepak Maurya² and Pinkey Dukpa¹¹School of Agriculture, ITM University, Gwalior (M. P.) – 475001, India²School of Agricultural Sciences, GD Goenka University, Sohna, Gurugram, Haryana -122 103, India

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Abstract

Present study was conducted to assess the genetic diversity, heritability, and genetic progress of twenty-five different genotypes of chilli. Analysis of variance revealed significant differences among the genotypes for all the characters. The higher estimates of PCV coupled with GCV were observed for leaf area (42.25% & 41.79%) and followed by fruit length (37.76% & 37.31%) total fruit yield per plant (37.55% & 37.24%) leaf chlorophyll (36.19% & 34.63%) and no. of fruit per plant (35.15% & 34.72%). However, the difference between the PCV and GCV was paltry, which indicating the high contribution of genetic components in phenotypic expression of these characters that provide higher selection efficiency. The higher estimates of broad sense heritability along with genetic advance recorded for plant height (97.99 & 50.50 %), leaf area (97.86 & 85.17 %), fruit length (97.67 & 75.97 %), no. of fruit per plant (97.56 & 70.63 %), average fruit weight (93.97 & 57.46 %), leaf length (92.83 & 36.68 %), leaf chlorophyll (91.54 & 68.25 %), which indicates the presence of additive gene action; hence selection could be employed for these traits and provide the opportunity for higher selection response.

Key words: Genetic advance, genotypes, heritability, variability and chilli.

Introduction

The chilli is cultivated as a tropical and subtropical crop and is an important part of the solanaceae family. It can be consumed as a vegetable or a spice. It also serves an industrial use as a result of the oleoresin extraction. The green fruit of the chilli plant is one of the best sources of anti-oxidant vitamins, including vitamins A, C, and E, which fight cancer. The major chilli-producing states in India include Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Maharashtra, Orissa, Tamil Nadu, Madhya Pradesh, and Rajasthan. India is the largest producer with (1.98 million tonnes) and contributes 43% of world chilli production, production by China, Ethiopia, Thailand, Pakistan and Bangladesh. One of the most significant vegetable crops is the chilli, which is prized for its flavour, pungency, scent, and taste. This crop allegedly has a large range of variability (Munshi and Behera, 2000). The degree of genetic variety in the existing material determines how genotypes can be improved. The interplay between the environment and the genotype results in phenotypic variability, which is frequently not an accurate reflection of the genotype. The extent of heritable and non-heritable components, as well as genetic metrics like genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation, heritability and genetic advance as a percentage of mean, have thus been tried to be determined in some of the quantitative characteristics of chilli. Studies on genetic diversity conducted by several researchers viz., PCV were observed to be higher than GCV for all the traits studied (Mishra *et al.*, 2001, Bendale *et al.*, 2006 and Kadwey *et al.*, 2016). PCV were higher for leaf area followed by fruit length, total fruit yield per plant, leaf chlorophyll and no. of fruit per plant (Gupta *et al.*, 2009). Highest GCV was observed for leaf area followed by fruit length, total fruit yield per plant, leaf chlorophyll and no. of fruit per plant. Heritability was found to be very high Heritability estimates were high for plant height, leaf area, fruit length, no. of fruit per plant, average fruit weight, leaf length, leaf chlorophyll (Bharadwaj *et al.*, 2007).

Materials and Methods

The materials for the study comprised of twenty-five Armour, Navtej, F1-1467, Pusa Jwala, F1-4868, Jersey-56, Sonal, Navajwala, F1-1474, NS-2701, VNR-332, CSB-8, Uttkal Ava, EC-341075, Albeli-222, EC-519630, CO-5661, Kashi Abha, IIHR-16, IC-119455, EC-622085, CMB-15, IC-119474, CMB-19, ISC-02 of chilli. During the Rabi season of 2022–2023, the cultivars were grown in a field experiment utilizing a randomized block design (RBD) with three replications in the crop Research CRC-II of the school of agriculture, ITM University Gwalior. To raise a good crop, proper agronomic procedures were used. Several observations on morphological features were made, including: days to first flowering, days to 50% flowering, days to first fruit setting, days to first fruit harvest, plant height (cm), number of primary branches per plant, days to maturity (mature green stage), days to maturity (red ripe stage), number of fruit

per plant, fruit length (cm), fruit diameter (cm), average fruit weight (g), total fruit yield per plant (g), total soluble solid (⁰B), leaf length, leaf area, leaf chlorophyll. Data were collected from five randomly chosen mature plants from each genotype. Each entry was transplanted into a plot measuring 2.5 m × 2.5 m with 60 x 50 cm spacing. The recommended agronomic package of practices and plant protection measures were applied to generate a high-quality crop. According to Burton (1952), the variance's constituents and coefficient of variation were calculated. Using the techniques proposed by Miller *et al.*, (1958), it was estimated that heritability in the broad sense and genetic advance as a percentage of mean existed.

Results and Discussion**Analysis of variance and mean performance of genotypes:**

Analysis of variance, general mean and range of variation for different characters are given in Table 1 and mean values of all genotypes for all characters are presented in Table 2. The studies indicated that there was a wide range of variability in the germplasm for all the characters under study viz., days to first flowering, days to 50% flowering, days to first fruit setting, days to first fruit harvest, plant height (cm), number of primary branches per plant, days to maturity (mature green stage), days to maturity (red ripe stage), number of fruit per plant, fruit length (cm), fruit diameter (cm), average fruit weight (g), total fruit yield per plant (g), total soluble solid (⁰B), leaf length, leaf area, leaf chlorophyll.

For all of the investigated characters, analysis of variance revealed a substantial difference between the accessions. Table 2 lists the degree of variation with regard to the range, mean, phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of variation, heritability, and genetic progress. The current analysis found that all of the analyzed traits varied significantly. Such a vast range of variance demonstrated the potential to increase the population of these traits, as originally mentioned by Cherian (2000). Numerous characters showed high coefficients of phenotypic (PCV) and genotypic (GCV) variance, the highest being for leaf area followed by fruit length, total fruit yield per plant, leaf chlorophyll and no. of fruit per plant. Similar results were also reported by (Mishra *et al.*, 2001, Bendale *et al.*, 2006 and Kadwey *et al.*, 2016). The high PCV and GCV observed are a result of their great variability, which in turn provides favorable selection opportunities. The lowest PCV and GCV were for days to maturity (Mature Red Stage), days to first fruit setting and days to maturity (Mature Green Stage), which was in conformity with the findings of Cherian (2000). Most of the characters' GCVs were close to their PCVs, showing a genotype's highly substantial influence on phenotypic expression and the environment's minimal influence. Estimates of heritability for the majority of the traits ranged from 43.59% for days to maturity (Mature Green Stage) to 98.38% for total fruit yield/plant (kg). Higher magnitude of heritability (>90 per cent) resulting from high GCV was also registered for total fruit yield/plant (kg), plant height

(cm), leaf area (cm²), fruit length (cm), no. of fruit per plant, average fruit weight (g), leaf length (mm) and leaf chlorophyll. Rajput *et al.*, (1981) obtained similar results for chilli (*Capsicum annuum* L.) in terms of fruits per plant and yield per plant, and Singh *et al.*, (1994) reported similar results for fruit characteristics. High heritability estimates suggest that there are numerous additive, fixable components present, which means that these traits may be enhanced by selection. The genetic development of the character chosen, together with heredity, determine the success of selection. For various biometric features, including yield/plant, fruit/plant, fruit weight, fruit girth, and fruit length, the study found high heritability together with high genetic progress. Several Yield features of the chilli (*C. annuum* L.) showed substantial heritability and genetic advancement, according to Jabeen *et al.*, (1998). According to prior research by Vijayalakshmi *et al.*, (1989), high heritability and little genetic advancement caused by non-additive gene activity were observed in the days leading up to the first blooming.

Coefficient of variability:

For 25 characteristics, estimates of the phenotypic, genotypic, and environmental coefficients of variability are shown in Table 3. In general, for all 25 characteristics, the magnitude of phenotypic coefficient of variability was greater than genetic coefficient of variability. We found a wide range of phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of variation. The highest phenotypic as well as genotypic coefficients of variation were observed in case of leaf area (42.25% and 41.79%) followed by fruit length (37.76% and 37.31%) total fruit yield per plant (37.55% and 37.24%) leaf chlorophyll (36.19% and 34.63%) and no. of fruit per plant (35.15% and 34.72%). However, the difference between the PCV and GCV was paltry, which indicating the high contribution of genetic components in phenotypic expression of these characters that provide higher selection efficiency, whereas moderate estimates of PCV and GCV were estimated for no. of primary branches per plant (23.96% and 22.70%), leaf length (19.18% and 18.48%) fruit diameter (18.43 % and 17.37%) and total soluble solid (15.82% and 14.57%). Similar, results have been reported by Singh and Singh (2017), Kumari *et al.*, (2017), Jogi *et al.*, (2017) and Gorka *et al.*, (2016). The phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of variations were lower for days to maturity (Mature Red Stage 6.97% and 6.13%) days to first fruit setting (5.33% and 4.59%) and days to maturity (Mature Green Stage 5.12% and 3.38%) low GCV and PCV for these traits indicated that there was less variation for this trait.

The characters exhibited wide variation for different characters may improve through selection or through hybridization. For all the traits under study in the current analysis, the phenotypic coefficient of variation was greater than the genotypic coefficient of variance. It could be because both genotypic and environmental heterogeneity are present at the phenotypic level. The majority of the characters had smaller discrepancies between PCV and GCV estimations, which suggested that these characters were more stable since they were less influenced by the environment. Similar to this study high PCV along with GCV were reported for days to first flowering, days to 50% flowering, days to first fruit setting, days to first fruit harvest, plant height (cm), number of primary branches/plant, days to maturity (mature green stage), days to maturity (red ripe stage), number of fruit/plant, fruit length (cm), fruit diameter (cm), average fruit weight (g), total fruit yield/plant (g), total soluble solid (°B), leaf length, leaf area, leaf chlorophyll.

Heritability broad sense:

Estimates of broad sense heritability (h²b) and genetic advance in per cent of mean for 25 characters in bitter melon genotypes are depicted in Table-3. Range of heritability estimates in broad sense varied from 43.59% to 98.38%. The heritability in broad sense ranged from 43.59 per cent in case of days to maturity (Mature Green Stage) to 98.38 percent for total fruit yield per plant (kg). Highest estimates of heritability (98.38%) were recorded for total fruit yield per plant. Heritability estimates were high for plant height (97.99%), leaf area

(97.86%), fruit length (97.67%), no. of fruit per plant (97.56%), average fruit weight (93.97%), leaf length (92.83%), leaf chlorophyll (91.54%) which indicates the presence of additive gene action; hence selection could be employed for these traits and provide the opportunity for higher selection response. whereas no. of primary branches per plant (89.78%), fruit diameter (88.80%), total soluble solid (84.80%), days to 50% flowering (81.87%) had moderate heritability. While days to maturity (MRS) (77.40%), days to first fruit harvest (75.70%), days to first fruit setting (73.93%) and days to first flowering (65.01%), had low heritability among all the characters.

Genetic advance:

The genetic advance was recorded highest in number of fruit per plant (35.29), plant height (31.17), leaf length (18.40), days to maturity (MRS) (13.96), days to 50% flowering (8.44), days to first fruit harvest (7.73), fruit length (6.79), days to first fruit setting (6.74), leaf area (6.68), days to maturity (MGS) (4.74), days to first flowering (3.86), leaf chlorophyll (3.62), fruit diameter (3.23), average fruit weight (3.05), number of primary branches per plant (2.90), total soluble solid (1.59) and total fruit yield per plant (0.91). When heritability is high and genetic progress is also high, this suggests that selection may be working since the heritability is most likely caused by additive gene effects. High heritability coupled with little genetic progress is a sign of non-additive gene activity. High heritability is a result of positive environmental influences rather than genotype, therefore selecting for such characteristics may not be advantageous. The character is controlled by additive gene effects when low heritability is present together with strong genetic progress. Due to significant contextual influences, there is poor heredity. In some situations, selection may be successful. Poor heritability and poor genetic progress suggest that the character is strongly impacted by environmental factors and that Selection would be unsuccessful in this case. Similar to this investigation heritability coupled with greater genetic advance was reported for number of fruits per plant, fruit yield per plant, average fruit weight, number of fruits per plant, average fruit weight.

Genetic advance in per cent of mean:

High estimates of genetic advance in per cent of mean (Table-3) was estimated for leaf area (85.17%), total fruit yield per plant (76.09%), fruit length (75.97%), number of fruit per plant (70.63%), leaf chlorophyll (68.25%), average fruit weight (57.46), plant height (50.50%) which indicates the presence of additive gene action; hence selection could be employed for these traits and provide the opportunity for higher selection response. Moderate genetic advance was estimated for number of primary branches per plant (44.31), leaf length (36.68), fruit diameter (33.72%), total soluble solid (27.64%), whereas, days to 50% flowering (14.72%), days to maturity (MRS) (11.11%), days to first flowering (10.78%), days to first fruit setting (8.12%), days to first fruit harvest (7.91%) and days to maturity (MGS) (4.60) showed low genetic advance in per cent of mean. Similar research on heredity and increased genetic advancement was reported for Plant height, leaf width (Singh *et al.*, 2017), days to flowering, fruit length, fruit diameter, number of fruits per plant, and fruit weight per plant (Yanti *et al.*, 2016) average fruit weight, and fruit yield per plant.

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Conclusion

Based on the overall results of the study, it was concluded that there was significant room for improving chilli cultivars because there was a broad range of variance across the germplasm lines for all the traits. The genotypic correlation coefficient was often marginally greater than the phenotypic correlation coefficient. This suggested that the environment played a minor effect on character expression. This may provide enough room for choosing chosen genotypes from the entire population. Average fruit weight exhibited the highest heritability in

conjunction with the greatest genetic progress, followed by the number of fruits per plant, fruit yield per plant, and fruit production per hectare. These characteristics demonstrated additive gene effects, showing a strong potential for selection response for any number of traits.

Information is more accurate when there is a high GCV together with a high heritability and genetic advance. The most significant quantitative characteristics to be taken into account for effective selection in chilli are total yield per plant, fruit length, fruit diameter, weight, and number of fruits per plant, according to the current study.

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Table 1: Analysis of variance, mean and range of characters

Characters	Mean	Range		Mean sum of square		
		Max	Min	Replication	Treatment	Error
Days to first flowering	35.77	31.00	39.33	1.01	19.08**	2.90
Days to 50 % flowering	57.36	51.33	64.67	1.24	66.11**	4.55
Days to first fruit setting	82.99	74.33	88.00	7.05	48.57**	5.11
Days to first fruit harvest	97.73	89.33	103.67	1.49	61.72**	5.97
No. of primary branches / plant	6.55	4.13	12.07	0.16	6.89**	0.25
Days to maturity (MGS)	103.13	95.33	108.67	21.97	52.22**	15.74
Days to maturity (MRS)	125.71	111.33	139.67	37.29	195.45**	17.34
Plant height (cm)	61.72	36.17	96.47	5.03	705.66**	4.80
Leaf area (cm ²)	7.84	4.45	18.78	0.06	32.43**	0.23
Leaf length (mm)	50.17	33.60	71.44	0.03	264.48**	6.63
Leaf Chlorophyll	5.31	3.21	11.15	0.18	10.45**	0.31
No. of fruit per plant	49.96	12.40	86.67	18.77	910.13**	7.53
Fruit length (cm)	8.94	4.99	15.57	0.17	33.67**	0.27
Fruit diameter (mm)	9.59	7.11	13.63	0.007	8.677**	0.350
Average fruit weight (g)	5.30	2.79	9.56	0.024	7.131**	0.149
Total soluble solid (B)	5.77	4.32	7.48	0.080	2.245**	0.127
Total fruit yield per plant (Kg)	1.20	0.61	2.15	0.013	0.603**	0.003

Table 2: Mean performance of 25 genotypes for seventeen characters in chilli.

S. No.	Genotypes	Days to first flowering	Days to 50 % flowering	Days to first fruit setting	Days to first fruit harvest	No. of primary branches / plant	Days to maturity (MGS)	Days to maturity (MRS)	Plant height (cm)	Leaf area (cm ²)
1	ARMOUR	37.00	54.67	88.00	103.67	5.60	106.67	139.67	79.87	8.89
2	NAVTEJ	33.67	55.00	85.67	102.67	6.53	106.33	136.33	77.73	11.25
3	SONAL	31.00	64.67	84.67	96.00	8.33	102.00	135.00	64.80	10.42
4	F1-1467	39.00	64.67	84.00	99.00	4.87	105.00	136.33	80.27	9.62
5	F1-1474	35.33	52.00	79.67	94.67	7.72	100.33	111.33	83.40	9.75
6	NS-2701	36.33	54.00	78.00	93.00	12.07	99.67	114.67	84.80	18.78
7	PUSA JWALA	35.33	53.33	85.33	100.33	4.13	103.33	127.33	96.47	13.81
8	F1- 4868	38.00	63.67	82.67	97.67	6.67	101.00	132.00	69.73	9.34
9	JERSEY-56	38.33	62.67	84.67	101.00	6.00	107.00	135.00	55.10	8.59
10	NAVAJWALA	37.00	63.33	83.00	98.00	5.13	104.00	135.00	60.77	8.90
11	CO-5661	33.00	52.67	85.67	100.67	7.56	106.33	127.00	43.17	5.98
12	KASHI ABHA	38.00	57.00	87.00	102.00	5.44	108.00	130.00	56.07	6.00
13	IIHR-16	37.67	58.67	87.67	102.67	7.74	108.67	125.33	58.70	5.12
14	VNR-332	37.67	51.33	75.00	90.00	5.72	96.00	113.67	51.10	6.22
15	CSB-8	31.67	59.00	77.67	92.67	6.37	98.67	121.67	49.20	5.27
16	IC-119455	38.67	58.00	81.33	96.33	6.93	102.33	127.33	62.73	7.28
17	UTTKAL AVA	34.67	52.00	82.33	97.33	5.48	103.33	116.33	58.60	4.45
18	EC-622085	35.67	53.00	84.00	99.00	7.49	105.00	127.00	60.97	5.25
19	CMB-15	33.00	54.00	86.67	101.67	6.61	104.33	119.33	55.50	5.76
20	EC-341075	34.33	53.33	80.00	91.67	6.59	97.67	117.67	60.63	5.93
21	IC-119474	39.33	62.67	85.33	100.33	5.96	105.67	128.67	36.17	4.79
22	ALBELI-222	37.67	57.00	77.67	89.33	5.77	95.33	118.33	38.97	7.15
23	CMB-19	34.00	61.00	86.67	101.67	5.91	107.67	127.67	49.30	6.67
24	ISC-02	37.00	64.00	87.67	102.67	6.94	108.67	121.00	65.67	5.98
25	EC-519630	31.00	52.33	74.33	89.33	6.19	95.33	119.00	43.27	4.75
	Mean	35.77	57.36	82.99	97.73	6.55	103.13	125.71	61.72	7.84
	Min	31.00	51.33	74.33	89.33	4.13	95.33	111.33	36.17	4.45
	Max	39.33	64.67	88.00	103.67	12.07	108.67	139.67	96.47	18.78
	SE(d) ±	1.39	1.74	1.85	1.99	0.41	3.24	3.40	1.79	0.40
	C.D. at 5%	2.81	3.51	3.72	4.02	0.83	6.53	6.86	3.61	0.80
	C.V. (%)	4.76	3.72	2.72	2.50	7.66	3.85	3.31	3.55	6.18

Table 3: Coefficient of variability, heritability, genetic advance, GCV and PCV for different characters.

Characters	Mean	Min.	Max.	var. (g)	var. (p)	Heritability (%)	GA	GA% mean	GCV (%)	PCV (%)	% cont.
Days to first flowering	35.77	31.00	39.33	5.39	8.29	65.01	3.86	10.78	6.49	8.05	8.24
Days to 50 % flowering	57.36	51.33	64.67	20.52	25.07	81.87	8.44	14.72	7.90	8.73	7.41
Days to first fruit setting	82.99	74.33	88.00	14.49	19.60	73.93	6.74	8.12	4.59	5.33	7.83
Days to first fruit harvest	97.73	89.33	103.67	18.59	24.55	75.70	7.73	7.91	4.41	5.07	8.81
No. of primary branches / plant	6.55	4.13	12.07	2.21	2.46	89.78	2.90	44.31	22.70	23.96	7.14
Days to maturity (MGS)	103.13	95.33	108.67	12.16	27.90	43.59	4.74	4.60	3.38	5.12	9.43
Days to maturity (MRS)	125.71	111.33	139.67	59.37	76.71	77.40	13.96	11.11	6.13	6.97	4.39
Plant height (cm)	61.72	36.17	96.47	233.62	238.42	97.99	31.17	50.50	24.76	25.02	3.61
Leaf area (cm ²)	7.84	4.45	18.78	10.73	10.97	97.86	6.68	85.17	41.79	42.25	3.92
Leaf length (mm)	50.17	33.60	71.44	85.95	92.58	92.83	18.40	36.68	18.48	19.18	5.39
Leaf Chlorophyll	5.31	3.21	11.15	3.38	3.69	91.54	3.62	68.25	34.63	36.19	5.71
No. of fruit per plant	49.96	12.40	86.67	300.87	308.40	97.56	35.29	70.63	34.72	35.15	4.12
Fruit length (cm)	8.94	4.99	15.57	11.14	11.40	97.67	6.79	75.97	37.31	37.76	4.21
Fruit diameter (mm)	9.59	7.11	13.63	2.78	3.13	88.80	3.23	33.72	17.37	18.43	5.43
Average fruit weight (g)	5.30	2.79	9.56	2.33	2.48	93.97	3.05	57.46	28.77	29.68	5.23
Total soluble solid (B)	5.77	4.32	7.48	0.71	0.83	84.80	1.59	27.64	14.57	15.82	5.67
Total fruit yield per plant (Kg)	1.20	0.61	2.15	0.20	0.20	98.38	0.91	76.09	37.24	37.55	3.46

Min.: Minimum, **Max.:** Maximum, **var. (g):** Variance (Genotypic), **var. (p):** Variance (Phenotypic), **GA:** Genetic advance, **GCV:** Genotypic coefficient of variation, **PCV:** Phenotypic coefficient of variation and **% cont.:** Per cent contribution.